
A Critical Discourse Analysis of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman's Historic 7th March Speech with Fairclough Model: A Political Studies Perspective

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Abstract

This world observes a lot of leaders and nationalist movements. Leaders like Nelson Mandela, Martin Luther King Jr, Abraham Lincoln, and Napoleon Bonaparte. They have all shines their own charismatic leadership and strong oratory power. All great movements in the timeframe of history were led by great influential leaders who could enhance and motivate people by their spectacular leadership quality. Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman was one of the personalities who could lead and guide a nation towards independence. His historic speech of 7th March 1971 is considered as one of the greatest oratories of the history of independence in Bangladesh. UNESCO recognized the great 7th March speech of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman as one of the world's documentary heritage in 2017. This speech shows the importance of political discourse and its analysis of influential heritage. This paper will analyze the historic speech with Fairclough model of a Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA).

Key words: Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman, Speech, 7th March, Fairclough, CDA.

Introduction

In linguistics, discourse refers to the term of language longer than a single sentence. Understanding discourse, one must analyze the use of spoken or written language in a social context. Discourse analysis mainly studies the language beyond a sentence. Critical Discourse Analysis mainly works on the language that studies the speech of a great orator. The historic 7th March speech mainly creates the way how a great leader like Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman delivers the language in a social context that inspires the millions of people toward independence. Critical Discourse Analysis was first introduced by the Lancaster School of Linguistics of which Norman Fairclough was the most prominent figure. Ruth Wodak also made a major contribution to this sector. This speech can be compared to the speech of Martin Luther King Jr, speech "I Have a Dream...". This historic 7th March speech gained international recognition when UNESCO enlisted that as part of the world's documentary heritage. It is included in the "Memory of the World Register" by UNESCO. From that perspective, the 7th March speech of 1971 can be considered an elegant part of the linguistic element of Critical Discourse Analysis. Van Dijk said that CDA examines the way social power is structured, and inequality is primitive, reorganized, and resisted by reference and talk in social and political context, in that point of view this historic 7th March speech enlisted political context.

Theoretical background

The speech had significant effects on the people of Bangladesh then East Pakistan at that time. It changed the scenario to seventy-five million people into people's army, prepared to fight at any cost

to save their motherland from the then-West Pakistan political hegemony. It ensures the momentum when the moment came in the early hours of 26th March 1971. This speech motivates people to fight for the sake of people as they get ready for the final call for independence. Bangabandhu's words were so inspirational to guide them in war, "I call upon you to turn every home into fortresses, confront the enemy with whatever you have, and close all roads for life, even if I am not around to give orders". The slogan of that time influences millions of people to join the war: [মা বোনেরা অস্ত্র ধরো বাংলাদেশ মুক্ত করো] (ma bonera ostro dhoro Bangladesh mukto koro) (Mothers and sisters, take up the arms and liberate Bangladesh); [সন্তানের রক্ত বৃথা যেতে দেব না], (sontaner rokto britha jhete debo na), (We will not let the child's blood go in vain); [বীর বাঙ্গালী অস্ত্র ধরো বাংলাদেশ স্বাধীন করো], (bir bangali ostro dhoro Bangladesh sadhin koro), (Brave Bengali hold arms and make Bangladesh independent).

Literature Review

Muhammad Nurul Huda (2020), In an article in The Daily Star, defines the speech as he followed the rules of "put the attributes first" while referring to quotations. In this article, former Vice Chancellor of the University of Dhaka, AAMS Arefin Siddique commented, "Bangabandhu completed his speech by 19 minutes and uttered almost 58 to 60 words per minute."

According to, Bangladesh Post, (2020), "The struggle this time is for our emancipation, the struggle this time is for the independence. He declared the call to turn every home into a fortress of resistance against the Pakistani oppressor. Sheikh Mujib clearly launched a non-cooperation movement against the Pakistani Army."

According to, Md. Shamsuddoha, (2020), in his article, pointed out that, "the public meeting about Bangabandhu on his historical 7th March speech was very crucial and he was very tactful about his speech because west Pakistani ruler can admit him any bad cause as his speech can lead them, secessionist."

From the above articles, the research gap is found that all the writers analyze the speech in literary perspective, but no one gives a linguistic aspect of this historic speech.

Theoretical framework

This part contains the theoretical concept of CDA by Fairclough:

Figure 1 – Fairclough model of Critical Discourse Analysis

Data and methods

The researcher used a qualitative approach to conduct this research. Moreover, data has been collected from some articles and newspapers. The typology of the study descriptive and explanatory both in linguistic form.

Result and Discussion

This section provides an analysis and discussion of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib's historic 7th March Speech. At first the text was used as linguistic aspect, then the text has been interpreted as situational aspect and at last the speech has been analyzing as sociopolitical aspect, as the researcher followed Fairclough model of CDA.

The speech as a text

The historic speech of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman 7th March 1971 (Department of films and Publications- Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2017) has been taken from this source.

Formal or Descriptive Linguistic Aspect of the Speech

Use of Exophoric Reference

It is happening when a word or phrase used outside of the discourse. In pragmatics it is also used as extralinguistic, that means not with the same text or endophora. Example of exophoric reference can be found as in the word, **I, Mine, you and We**.

In the speech we can find this reference as,

1. আমরা আমাদের জীবন দিয়ে চেষ্টা করেছি (amra amder jibon diye chesta korechi).

(We tried with our lives).

2. আমি প্রেসিডেন্ট ইয়াহিয়া খান সাহেবের সাথে দেখা করেছি। (ami President Yahya khan Saheber sathey dekha korechi). **(Today I met President Yahya Khan).**

3. আমাদের ন্যাশনাল এসেম্বলি বসবে, আমরা সেখানে শাসনতন্ত্র তৈরি করবো এবং এদেশকে আমরা গড়ে তুলবো। (amader national assembly bosbey, amra shasontontro toiri korbo abong adeshkey gorey tulbo). **(Our National assembly will sit today. We will make the Constitution there and we will build this country).**

4. আমি, আমি প্রধানমন্ত্রিত্ব চাই না। আমরা এদেশের মানুষের অধিকার চাই। (ami,ami prodhanmontritto chai na amra adesher manuser odhikar chai). **(I Myself don't want Prime Ministership. We want rights of the common people of this country).**

5. আমরা যখন মরতে শিখেছি তখন কেউ আমাদের দাবায়া রাখতে পারবেনা। (amra jhokon mortey shekechi thokon keu amder dabaya rakhtey parbeyna).

(Since we learn to die, no one can abstain from us).

6. আমি বললাম আমরা আলোচনা করবো (ami bollam amra alochona korbo).

(I said that we will discuss the matter).

7. ভাইয়েরা আমার, (vaiyera amar).

(Brothers of mine).

8. আমি অনুরোধ করছি। আপনারা আমাদের ভাই। (ami aunurodh korechi apnara amder vai).

(I am requesting you; all of you are my brothers.).

Use of Anaphoric Reference

It means that a word in a certain text refers to other ideas in the text for its meaning. Here in this speech (he) used as anaphoric reference, For example,

তিনি বললেন দেশে শাসনতন্ত্র দেবেন, গণতন্ত্র দেবেন। আমরা মেনে নিলাম। তারপর অনেক ইতিহাস হয়ে গেল, নির্বাচন হল। (tini bollen deshey shashontontro deben gonotontro deben amra meney nilam, tarpor onek itihash hoye gelo, nirbachon holo).

(He said he would give us constitution and democracy to the nation. We agreed on that point. Thereafter the rest is history, the election has occurred).

Parallelism

In linguistic parallelism, is known as parallel structure or parallel construction of a sentence. It is a balance within a sentence in similar phrases or clauses that has the same grammatical structure in context. In rhetorical speech parallelism gives importance to gregarious speech. Here in this speech, we can find the parallelism,

1. এবারের সংগ্রাম আমাদের মুক্তির সংগ্রাম, এবারের সংগ্রাম স্বাধীনতার সংগ্রাম।

(abrer songram amder muktir songram abarer songram sadhinotar songram).

(Struggle this time is the struggle for our emancipation. Struggle this time is the struggle for our independence).

2. সাত কোটি মানুষকে দাবায়া রাখতে পারবানা। আমরা যখন মরতে শিখেছি তখন কেউ আমাদের দাবায়া রাখতে পারবানা। (sat kuti manuskey dabaya rakhtey parbana, amra jhokon mortey shikechi thokon keu amder dabaya rakhtey parbana).

(No one keep seven crores of people subjugated. Since we have learnt to die, no one can subjugate us).

3. রক্ত যখন দিয়েছি রক্ত আরো দেবো। এদেশের মানুষকে মুক্ত করে ছাড়বো ইনশাআল্লাহ। (rokto jhokon diyechi thokon rokhto aro debo adesher manuskey mukto korey charbo inshallah).

(Since we have given blood, we will give more blood. By the grace of Allah, we will surely liberate the people of this country).

Use of reframing in the speech

Reframing is way of going back in the speech and re interpreting the meaning of the first sentence. Here, in this speech we can find reframing,

(ভাইয়েরা আমার ২৫ তারিখে এসেম্বলি কল করেছে। রক্তের দাগ শুকায় নাই। আমি ১০ তারিখে বলে দিয়েছি, ওই শহীদদের রক্তের ওপর পাড়া দিয়ে আরটিসিতে মুজিবর রহমান যোগদান করতে পারেনা। এসেম্বলি কল করেছেন আমাদের দাবি মানতে হবে।).

(vaiera amar 25 tarikhey assembly call korechey. Rokter dag sukay nai. Ami 10 tarikh boley diyechi oi shoيدر rokter upor para diye rtc tey Mujibur Rahman jogdan kortey parena. Assembly call korechen amder dabi mantey hobey).

(The Assembly has called on the 25th of March. The signs of bloods have not yet dried. I had clearly said on the 10th March that Mujibur Rahman can't join RTC, treading the bloods of martyrs. Since you called the assembly, you need to accept my demands).

Here in this sentence Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Reinterpreting the first sentence as reframing.

Interpretation of the situational aspect

The situational aspect of CDA in Fairclough model means contextual or mindset of the speaker in the speech. It involves cause, state, subplot, `experience and result that interpret the text. The purpose of the public speech is to set an agenda which is clearly found on 7th March speech. The subplot speech is interrogative. There were six interrogative clauses in the speech, Sheikh Mujibur Rahman used those WH questions in dialogical manner to reinforce his subject as sub plot. His speech was both declarative mood and imperative mood in manner. For example,

1. কী অন্যায্য করেছিলাম আমরা? (ki onnay korechilam amra) (What wrong did we commit?).

2. কী পেলাম আমরা? (ki pelam amra) (What did we get?).

3. কিসের রাউন্ড টেবিল? (kiser round table) (RTC for what?).

4. কার সঙ্গে বসবো? (kar songey bosbo) (Who do we sit with?).

5. যারা আমার মানুষের বুকের রক্ত নিয়েছে তাদের সাথে বসবো? (jara amr manuser buker rokto niyechey tader sathey bosbo) (Shall I sit with those people who spilled the blood of my people?).

6. আপনাদের কী আমার উপর বিশ্বাস আছে? (apnader ki amar upor bissas achey) (Do you have faith in me?).

Use of situational context in numeric number:

Situation words	The number of appearances	The percentage of appearance
Brothers of Mine (vaiera amar)	2	16%
You know (apnara janen)	3	25%
Blood (rokto)	7	58%
Independence (mukti)	4	33%
Assembly	8	66%

(The calculation is based on 1200 words that Sheikh Mujibur Rahman uttered in his speech)

Socio political or explanatory Aspect of the speech

At the end of the speech when Bangabandhu said that, set up action committees under the leadership of Awami league in all villages and townships and remain prepared with what we have. By this line he tried to engage the audience with high frequency of communication skills and the art of oratory skills. The disunity of two Pakistan's became more fatal because of military interventions of the then two Pakistan's. The East Pakistan's side dominated by the West Pakistani military rulers. The West Pakistan government didn't allow radio and television to broadcast this speech but somehow some crew of East Pakistan recorded this historic speech and distribute the message among the larger audience. In Fairclough model explanatory comes when the speech becomes more engaged in audience. He mentioned four conditions to join the assembly on 25th March and also gave directives of civil disobedient movement in the speech and by this directive he explains the situation to mass audience for preparing the independence and defend their country still their last breath.

Conclusions

The liberation war of this country was one of the epoch-making events not only in the history of Bangladesh but also in the history of the world. This birth of a nation gave the people a new hope and aspiration to move forward. Now Bangladesh is one of the developing nations which will remove from LDC by 2026. This paper tries to give a Critical Discourse Analysis view of the speech, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman delivered on 7th March 1971. This speech is analyzed through the CDA model of Norman Fairclough. In this paper the researcher shows the descriptive, Interpretation and explanatory linguistic aspects of the CDA model. In addition to that, this speech is the precursor of the independence of Bangladesh.

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